

HOUSING@21.eu: EMERGING FORMS OF LIVING AND HOUSING IN 21st century EUROPE
Coordinator Partner: Arquitectura La Salle- Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona-Spain
Erasmus Intensive Programme 2003-2006
29467-IC-3-2004-1-ES-ERASMUS-IPUC-1

FINAL REPORT

Project Coordinator: Leandro Madrazo

1. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the intensive programme HOUSING@21.EU are twofold:

1. To learn to grasp the complexities and interdependencies of the factors transforming our way of life, responding to these challenges with new forms of housing.
2. To develop a pedagogic methodology using a web-based learning platform especially created for this project.

The transforming factors are considered at three different levels: social, economic and technological. Dwelling is addressed from three different scales: individual, communal and urban. This three-by-three structure, which is applied both to the research and the design work, enables students and faculty to grasp the complexity of the issues involved in the production of housing in contemporary European societies.

The most innovative aspect has been the development of a pedagogic methodology associated to a web-based environment created for this IP. This web platform, developed by the research group ARC Arquitectura i Enginyeria La Salle specifically for this IP, allows students and faculty from the five participating institutions to carry out a joint research on study cases through the Internet.

The first release of the environment was already operating during the first year of the programme. Following the evaluation of the first year's implementation, we proceeded to enhance and improve the web for the second year's programme. For the third year, we have been able to benefit from having a tested web environment with the necessary functionality to be used already from the start of the programme's activities.

The activities of the IP have been integrated into the existing teaching programmes, individually at each institution, and collectively, with each partner contributing to the creation of a common knowledge space, based on the Web. The European dimension of this project will very much depend on the possibility of further developing and consolidating the knowledge space started. A consistent application of the web-based environment in the future will enable the participant institutions to overcome the existing division between individual and collective activities, achieving a truly integrated pedagogic structure. In order to pursue that goal, a new consortium has been created to develop the learning environment created in this IP and transform it into a European virtual campus dedicated to the analysis and study of housing (see CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK).

2. ORGANISATION OF THE PROGRAMME'S ACTIVITIES

A coordination meeting had place in Barcelona, on March 17th 2006, with the participation of the project coordinators from the five participant institutions. In this meeting the common strategies were defined, the design topic was chosen, and schedules and objectives to achieve were agreed on.

Following the strategy defined in the coordination meeting, the pedagogic work was carried out in this sequence:

1. Independently, in the teaching programmes of each institution (March-May)
2. Collaboratively, in the joint research on study cases on the Internet (April-June)
3. Jointly, at the Workshop in Barcelona, dedicated to the design of innovative housing (3-14th, July).

2.1. Independent work at each institution (March-May 2006)

During the academic year 2005_06, each institution carried out the following pedagogic activities related to the subject-matter of this IP:

- HFT, Fachhochschule Stuttgart: Students carried out the analysis of cases working under the direction of the local coordinator. The appropriate use of computer media in the representation of cases was particularly stressed.
- W&K, Sint-Lucas, Ghent/Brussels: The students from the first master degree could choose an elective course, that took place during 12 weeks, 3 hours a week in the second semester.
- BTU, Bialystok: integrated design studio on multifamily social housing, carried out on the second year of studies, aimed at looking for new functional standards and urban solutions. Students were particularly encouraged to take into account the relationship between housing and city.
- UL, Liverpool: participating students were instructed to actively develop case studies which were relevant to the study of mass housing. Analytical projects were chosen, researched and entirely developed by students. The project was a separate component to existing school curriculum.
- URL, Barcelona: design and maintenance of the web-based platform; seminar on housing analysis during the Spring-Summer semester led by Prof. Leandro Madrazo; organization of the Workshop.

2.2. Collaborative work on the internet: case study analysis (April-June 2006)

Besides these independent activities, all partners have participated in the research work on cases of study, carried out on the Internet using the web-based platform HOUSING@21.eu (www.housing21eu.net)

An analysis of representative housing cases was carried out on a web-based platform especially created for this project. The ultimate goal was to identify critical issues that would be later discussed at the joint seminar. The case study analysis was done in two parts: first, each student proposed and analyzed up to five housing projects; second, collaborative works were done using the information obtained.

2. 2.1 Case study analysis

Participating students at each institution, under the guidance of their tutors, selected 3-5 housing projects (built or un-built) to be analyzed. The analyses were submitted to the web-based platform. The description of a case study consists of graphics (plans, sections, elevations, photos) and text information (description of the case following the six-fold structure: social, economic and technological levels; individual, communal and urban dimensions; keywords and bibliographic references).

In this third year, a different working strategy has been carried out at Sint-Lucas. Students have worked in groups rather than individually during this stage of the work. Due to the large amount of students that wanted to collaborate (42 students) it seemed to be more interesting to group these students (7 groups of 6 students). Each group was assigned a theme taken from the levels and dimensions the site is organised with: social, economical and technological levels and the individual, communal and urban dimensions. Each group searched for new case studies and cases already inserted in the database that fitted their chosen theme the best. During the courses the students presented their work to the whole group using the website www.housing21eu.net.

One group was particularly special because they got the theme "graphics". The goal of this group was trying to define a graphical standard which could be used by everyone to give a sense of scale and an insight in the logic of a housing scheme. They managed to develop a graphical code (colours and cake diagrams) to, only by using the scale-less plans on the site, to give the viewer of the site an idea of the scale and plan logic of the cases.

A next step into the course was the students adding comment a the other groups' cases. Until now for each newly introduced case only one level or dimension was taken care of. By swapping each new case added to the different groups the theoretical inputs were completed. This was very interesting to see how students had to read others inputs and to reflect on these because they were obliged to complete the cases.

During this whole process, the local coordinator, Prof. Jao Smet, was able to stimulate and control the inputs not only by the using the website of the program but also by using their own intern e-learning tool called "toledo" to communicate with students to give them online lecture and input.

The following table summarizes the content which students have submitted to the case study library in the three years of the programme.

	2003-2004	2004-2005	2005-2006	TOTAL

CASES OF STUDY	71	110	118	299
IMAGES	796	1623	195	4369
KEYWORDS	87	196	128	411
BIBLIOGRAPHIC ENTRIES	100	58	68	226
URL REFERENCES	54	31	87	172
GROUPS	14	9	11	34
DISCUSSION FORUM ENTRIES	Not implemented	7	15	22
CASE STUDY FORUM ENTRIES	36	20	50	106
E-MAILS	190	179	568	937

2.2.2 Collaborative Work

Once the study of cases was completed, an on-line collaboration started with the goal of promoting interaction and knowledge exchange between participants. The activities followed this sequence:

- 1- Adding information to another student's study case (images; keywords)
- 2- Adding comments to the study case forums.
- 3- Searching for relations among study cases (grouping cases).
- 4- Participating in the forum discussions about particular cases and about generic housing topics.

The collaborative work contributed to make participants know each other before the face-to-face contact at the Workshop (see attached web-site description).

2.2.3 Manifesto of housing in 21st century

In this third year, we have introduced an additional task to work as a nexus between the on-line collaborative work and the joint workshop: each student should end the preparatory phase with a manifesto describing his/her personal views about the issue of housing in 21st century. The manifesto would be posted in the workshop's web site prior to the start of the workshop.

3. JOINT WORKSHOP: HOUSING AT PLAÇA DE LES GLORIES, BARCELONA

3.1 Objectives

In the first year's program, we chose as a design topic three sites located at three different districts in the city of Barcelona. In the second year, we enlarged the scale of the interventions, selecting three large areas in the periphery of the city which were going to undergo a process of urban transformation. For the third and last year of the program, we have selected a central area in the city of Barcelona –plaça de les Glories Catalanes- which is going to be renewed according to the plans recently made public by the city's urban planning office.

As it was planned by Cerdà, Plaça de les Glòries was a formless place resulting from the intersection of traffic lines. In the original plan, three major avenues intersect at that place: Avinguda Diagonal, Avinguda Meridiana and Gran Via. With this intersection of three major avenues, the Cerdà plan created a difficult urban problem which has never been properly solved: the lack of precise boundaries and its undefined scale has made its integration in the orthogonal grid extremely difficult.

The main goal of the latest plan to solve the problem of plaça de les Glòries is to transform a traffic intersection into a public place which can be used by the inhabitants of the district. The elevated highway ring which exists nowadays will be demolished and a public square will be created. In the new plan, the traffic circulating through Avinguda Diagonal will go around the place, at the surface level, while cars circulating through Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes will circulate underneath. Following the prevailing city model –which favors a dense city with a mixed of functions-, planners want to endow this area of the city with an urban character by combining offices, cultural facilities, and housing.

The design task for the students was to define the role of housing in the transformation of the area, making proposals which take into consideration the characteristics of the place: centrality, accessibility, boundary conditions.

3.2 Organization of working groups

Like in previous years, students were organized in groups of three, each one from a different university. However, unlike previous two workshops, the groups were not created randomly but it was left to the students to choose their partners. In order to make students know each other, they were asked to explain in public their manifesto which they had previously published in the web. In this way, students had the opportunity to choose their partners based on their own affinities.

3.3 Organization of the lectures

The Workshop began Monday, July 3th, with a lecture by Prof. Amador Ferrer, Professor of Urban Planning and Urban Design at Arquitectura La Salle, about the history of the urban development of the city of Barcelona. In this lecture, Prof. Ferrer explained the Cerdà Plan, and the successive attempts to solve the urban problem created at the Plaça de les Glòries. At the end of the lecture, he presented the latest plan of urban renewal for the area developed by the city's urban planning office.

After the lecture, students and teachers went on a bus tour to visit the project site as well as recently renewed districts in the city where housing has played a major role in the renovation (Fort Pienc, Fòrum 2004, Vil.la Olímpica) as well as some well-established, traditional neighborhoods (Eixample, Barceloneta, Gràcia).

During the second day, there were two lectures during the morning sessions. The first one was given by the architect Amadeu Iglesias, Managing Director of the Metropolitan Institute of Real State (IMPSOL). He presented several mid-large scale housing projects promoted by public authorities in nearby cities around Barcelona. In these projects, one of the major concerns of the urban planners and architects has been the integration of housing in the urban tissue (relationship of buildings with the street; public spaces and housing; car access and parking). The housing typologies of these projects were rather conventional mostly because of the reluctance from inhabitants to change their mode of living.

The second lecture, by Prof. Leandro Madrazo, addressed the problem of modern housing from anthropological, sociological and philosophical view points.

The rest of the lectures took place during the second week, so that students could start with the design project. The second series of lectures were given by participating professors. Prof. David Stokes, from Liverpool, reflected upon the nature of the creative process, illustrated with examples of projects from practicing architects and designers from varying disciplines and his own personal design work. Prof. Jao Smet explained the pedagogic strategy they followed in Sint Lucas to integrate the web-repository of cases into their teaching. Finally, Prof. Horst Sondermann presented different projects made by students from FH Stuttgart for the competition "The Topography of Terror", to build a documentation centre in Berlin, on a site where there had been the seat of the security services of the nazi regime.

3.4 Structure of the design process

The process for students to carry out the design project was structured in two parts:

- 1- Elaboration of a design scheme, during the first week, step-by-step through a series of short tasks.
- 2- Development of the scheme, during the second week, concluding with a final presentation the last day of the workshop.

TASK 1 (Deadline Wednesday 5th). The first task was to propose a design strategy for the site and the program to be carried out. Students were asked to reflect on the following questions:

- What are the limits of the site? Where does the site begin and end?
- What role can housing play in the definition of the character of the place?
- What image of the city you foresee in this site?
- What would be the daily life of the people (also yourself) living in that area?
- What do point, line and plane mean in this site?

Work could be presented in any media (digital and physical, 2d or 3d, images and photomontages,...), properly applied.

The work was also submitted in digital form to the workshop website using the available submission form (see <http://www.housing21eu.net/workshop3>).

TASK 2 (deadline Thursday 6th). In the second task students were asked to move from conceptual diagramming and urban analysis to thinking about the intervention in the site, meaning:

- Defining the boundaries between the site and the rest of the city
- Defining the role that housing -in conjunction with open spaces and public facilities- would play in the materialization of those boundaries materialize these limits.
- Characterizing the different boundary conditions (hard or soft edges, massive or transparent limits, vertical or horizontal barriers,...) using different forms of housing (for families, for singles, for elderly people) (and, at the same time, create a unified urban area.

The requirements for this presentation were:

- Massing model to be inserted in the site 1:2000
- Sections and plans of the master plan
- Description of housing types (block, tower,) and corresponding user types (family, single,)

TASK 3 (deadline Friday 7th). The third task focused on the proposal of housing forms which contribute to create a sense of place in the Glòries area. Proposals should address simultaneously two issues:

- 1- the urban configuration of the area of Glòries. This means: 1. to accept the plan proposed by the City Urban Planning office, as it is 2. to make an alternative plan, at a schematic level, without trying to solve all of the complexity of issues involved (traffic, landscaping, infrastructures,...).
- 2- the proposal of housing forms in the selected areas of the proposed urban scheme. If the urban model chosen is the one proposed by the city, then it is enough to propose housing forms in the areas foreseen by the plan.

As a link between urban scale and housing scale, some reflections should be made about the connectivity between the new open spaces in Glòries and the existing spaces in the surrounding city fabric (the connection with the neighborhoods; the flow of pedestrians in, out and through Glòries area; the connection with the sea,...)

The requirements for this presentation:

- massing model to be inserted in the site 1:2000
- sections and plans of the master plan 1:500, showing the relation between building and open spaces
- housing plans, elevations, sections, 1:200
- representations (photomontages, collages) of the buildings integrated in the context
- representations (photomontages, collages) which anticipate the atmosphere and character of the open spaces

During the rest of the workshop, each group continued developing the scheme developed during the first week. Participating professors could discuss with all groups the development of the proposals. This way, all groups could have the opportunity to discuss their projects with all participating professors, so that they could compare and assess the diversity of their comments and appreciations.

The final presentation of the projects took place on Friday 14th, the last day of the workshop. Each group presented their project in public, using a digital and traditional media. Final proposals have been published in the web site of the workshop.

4. PARTICIPATION AND CREDITS

Students and teachers were selected at each institution, according to the following criteria:

-HFT, Fachhochschule Stuttgart: Students were selected from the upper courses. Professors who have a capacity to work both on architectural design and with ICT were appointed as tutors.

- W&K, Sint-Lucas, Ghent/Brussels: The students were selected from among the participants in the elective course Housing@21.eu in Ghent. The selection criteria for participation in the Barcelona Workshop was the quality of the preparatory work produced during course.

- BTU, Bialystok: Students were selected among the candidates from the last four years of studies according to the results achieved in the design studio courses, knowledge of English language and their

interest in housing. Selected students attended an additional course dedicated to analyzing housing study cases and working on the IP project web-site. Professors were selected on the basis of their knowledge of housing design and personal will to participate in an international Erasmus programme.

- UL, Liverpool: Students were selected from the second year of the BA Architecture course on the basis of their demonstrated enthusiasm for housing and their ability to work in a group situation, both as participants and facilitators. The students were selected on the basis of the abilities within CAD and overall design skills and by consequence their individual design abilities and personal ambitions were amongst the high achievers. Tutors were selected both for their knowledge and experience of housing design and their willingness to participate in an international Workshop.

- URL, Barcelona: Students were selected among the candidates from the last three courses of the five-year program, on the basis of the grades obtained in the design studio courses, and knowledge of English language. Candidate students worked together in an elective course, dedicated to analyzing housing study cases. Participant professors were selected on the basis of their knowledge of housing design, and their personal interest in participating in an international Workshop.

ECTS points have been awarded to students by the following institutions:

- HFT, Fachhochschule Stuttgart: 4 ECTS points
- W&K, Sint-Lucas, Ghent/Brussels: 3 ECTS points (for the preparatory work and 3 points in the 2nd Master Degree for the Summer Workshop)
- BTU, Bialystok: 4 ECTS points
- UL, Liverpool: 7.5 ECTS points
- URL, Barcelona: 3 ECTS points

5. OUTPUTS

1. Web-based learning environment (SEE ATTACHED DOCUMENTATION DESCRIBING THE WEB PLATFORM)

- www.housing21eu.net
Web site platform to carry out the analysis of study cases in collaboration. It has been programmed with DHTML, CGI scripting in PERL connected to a MySQL relational database.
- www.housing21eu.net/workshop3
Web site containing the Workshop activities, site descriptions, web log and final design proposals.

The design and implementation of a web-platform of this scope goes beyond the objectives of this IP, and it has only been possible through the commitment of the research group ARC Arquitectura i Enginyeria La Salle, Universitat Ramon Llull.

2. Publications

A syllabus was produced and given to participants at the beginning of the Workshop (see attached documentation). It contained information about the sites, examples of recent housing buildings in Barcelona, and a selection of articles on contemporary housing.

3. Dissemination

- Internet

1. Workshop's website. As in the previous two workshops, we have created a website to promote and exhibit the work done:

<http://www.housing21eu.net/workshop3>

2. ISOC, Socrates Projects Database. A summary of the project's activities is published in this database.

<http://www.isoc.siu.no/isocii.nsf/projectlist/29467>

- Media

An article by the journalist Montse Capella reporting the activities of the third workshop has been published at the newspaper *Actual*, July 20th, 2006, p. 35 (SEE ARTICLE ANNEXED)

6. EVALUATION

The design proposals were discussed in a final critique, carried out during the last day of the workshop, with the participation of all faculty members. Isabela de Renteria, Professor at Arquitectura La Salle, acted as a external guest critic.

Quality of results was diverse among the different groups, due to the different level of skills of the students and to their capacity to work together. The project site turned out to be particularly difficult for most of students due to the urban complexity.

6. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

These are some reflections after the experience of conducting this third year of the programme:

- the success of the preparatory stage of the programme (case study analysis using the web-based environment) depends very much on the skills and motivation of the teachers in charge. It is crucial that the teachers are able to develop their own pedagogic methodologies which fit with their way of teaching. As an example of good practice in this regard, we can mentioned the strategy adopted by Prof. Jao Smet during this year, which was very succesful in motivating students and in using the web resources in an effective and productive manner.
- the success of the workshop cannot just be measured against the results / production of schemes from the various groups on a creative level. The act of living / working outside of the UK is invaluable. Studying within the eclectic urban fabric of barcelona was a rich experience for most students due to the exposure to architectural projects which are not witnessed within their everyday lives. Also, it was positive for students the experience of working with other students from different cultural backgrounds and approaches in developing a common project which due to the format of the groups must address individual / group working methods in their management of conflicting design agendas.
- the selected design project to carry out in the workshop turned out to be too difficult for some students. Most of them lacked the necessary knowledge in urban planning that was necessary to understand the limits and scale of the site. As a result, project proposals failed to achieve a balance between urban issues and architectural ones. Some students got trapped were not able to overcome the urban scale, because of the lack of conceptual tools and urban planning skills. Partly because of the urban complexity, housing issues could not be addressed with the depth that it was desired.
- the project was vast, complex and problematic for the less experienced student. The intervention within the site was amplified by some groups desire to address all issues revealed from their analysing mass housing within the context of contemporary design solutions, which was evidently over ambitious. The complexity of the context impacted on their time management and effectively their designs were lacking in detail and remained master plans geared around circulation patterns for automobiles. Another week to the programme would have been ideal and ample time to transpose their raw conceptual statements, essentially focussed on image, into believable scenarios for mass housing within urban fabric. This demands greater time as addresses detail and execution of innovative design relative to planning concerns. Therefore, their results lacked depth as concepts remained untested by the rigour of pragmatism and technique. However, the students were encouraged to continue to develop their projects through electronic media.
- students have demonstrated a high level of skill in using digital imaging and modeling, which enables them to quickly visualize and present ideas. However, this facility to visualize might provoke that truly architectural issues –like building and urban scale, construction and assembling of building components- are neglected because of a negative influence of imaging.
- one of the challenges for the educators in these intensive programs is to create working processes that enables an heterogeneous group of students to work together effectively and creatively. Some students, however, seem to dislike this focusing on processes and would rather prefer to test the knowledge they have already acquired designing a project.
- the diverse level of motivation of the participating students is one of the decisive factors for the success of group work. Even though this time we let students to choose their partners, this did not always result in a harmonious collaboration. Differences in skills, background, language, and motivation are obstacles that need to be overcome and managed to achieve a successful collaboration among students. As in previous years, while some groups could work very effectively there were others in which collaboration was difficult,

or even impossible. However, to develop a capacity to work in a team, particularly doing creative tasks like architectural design, is one of the challenges and opportunities that these Intensive programs provide.

- with regard to the understanding of the problem of housing in contemporary European societies, we are convinced that the conceptual framework we have adopted for the analysis of housing cases –space dimension: individual, communal, urban; factors of transformation: social, economic, technological– can help to understand the problem of housing in its whole complexity, beyond purely objectual or technological considerations which reduce dwelling to a matter of building shelter using the most effective production systems. We have stressed the fact that the problem of housing cannot be isolated from the problem of the city, and that private space cannot be detached from public space. With this conceptual structure we have provided a different way of approaching the study of housing, at a European level.

- with regard to pedagogic methods, with this three-year program we have initiated an new learning space around the issue of housing, using ICT to create new pedagogic models overcoming disciplinary and institutional boundaries. We think this model could serve as a reference for future projects, particularly those aiming at the creation of a European space of education. In this regard, this intensive program has given us the opportunity to experiment with new possibilities of using ICT in architectural education, at a European level.

- in particular, the digital repository containing 300 cases of study described and analyzed by students is one of the most significant outputs of this Intensive program. The ultimate intention is to allow all architecture schools free access to this repository. However, before doing that, it would be necessary to edit the existing content in order to ensure the liability and quality of the data (sources, language correctness).

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

After the experience of this three-year intensive program, the five participating institutions have carried out joint pedagogic activities with the objective of investigating existing forms of housing models in Europe and to propose alternative forms for the 21st century.

The result of this work has been the development and implementation of an innovative teaching model to address the issue of housing at a European scale. The learning activities which have been carried out over three consecutive academic years have encompassed courses at the participating institutions (architectural design, history and theory, urban planning), physical mobility (a joint design workshop has been organized each year for students to develop alternative forms of housing) and virtual mobility (documentation and analyses of housing cases have been carried out collaboratively at the web-based environment). During these three years, 75 students (who have been granted ECTS credits for their participation) and 17 professors (of architectural design, history, theory, construction and urban planning) in the five Schools have participated in the learning activities, which have result in the collaborative construction of a digital repository of over 250 cases of study, including housing examples from most European countries, most of them designed or built throughout the 20th century up to the current time. These results are a testimony of the enthusiasm and commitment that students have put into the project.

This teaching model constitutes a unique experience in recent architecture education in Europe. The pedagogic methodology takes advantage of the potential of ICT to create a learning space to study housing at a European scale which overcomes geographic boundaries (five European countries collaborate in the process of knowledge construction) and disciplinary boundaries (professors from different subject matters participate in the learning activities) supporting a constructivist model of education that places the student at the center of the learning activity. The constructive interaction between academic activities and activities carried out at the web-based learning space constitutes one of the strengths of this teaching model. This interaction of physical and virtual activities, along with the structured sequence of tasks, moving from the analysis of existing cases to the design of new proposals, has proved to be pedagogically meaningful both for students and faculty.

In order to continue the work that has been initiated in this IP, we have created a new, enhanced consortium to elaborate a research proposal for the development of a virtual campus under the auspices of the eLearning program. In this consortium two of the partners participating in this IP- Arquitectura La Salle and Sint-Lucas-, will work together with four other institutions from France, United Kingdom, Slovakia and Portugal. The proposal was submitted in May 2006 and the results will be known at the end of the year.